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Hydroclimatological Data Requirements and Availability

NBSPLUS - NBS services promoting local biodiversity, well-being
and scalable solutions

Evidence Brief

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- **Hydrological and hydrodynamic modelling for NbS scenario analysis can be conducted as either long-term or event-based simulations, each with distinct input requirements**
- **Recommendations and guidelines for hydroclimatological input data vary significantly across and within countries**
- **Both historical observations and future climate projections are widely available through national services and global datasets**

Introduction

This brief outlines the requirements for, and availability of, hydroclimatological data used in hydrological and hydrodynamic modelling to support the design and performance evaluation of nature-based solutions (NbS).

The analysis draws on three case studies located in Spain, Canada and Sweden

(Table 1), and is generalized to ensure broader applicability across diverse settings. While the project primarily focuses on flood risk reduction, the findings are also relevant for other hydroclimatological hazards, including drought and, to a lesser extent, heat stress.

Table 1. Overview of case studies, models and hydroclimatological inputs.

Case study (primary focus)	Models	Historical input	Future input
Albufera lake, Valencia, Spain (pluvial flooding, water scarcity, water quality)	AQUATOOL modules: - EVALHID (hydrology) - SIMGES (water management) - GESCAL (water quality)	Daily precipitation, temperature and radiation (from local stations and national gridded data)	Climate projections (down to daily and basin scale resolution) from national portals
Rivere du Nord, Quebec, Canada (flooding, erosion, water quality)	New hydrological model under construction System Dynamics modelling tool (e.g., Vensim; Stella)	Daily precipitation, temperature and radiation (from local and national station networks)	Climate projections from global (~25 km) and regional (~10 km) datasets
Riseberga stream, Malmö, Sweden (pluvial flooding)	Lisflood FPP (hydrodynamic model with “rain-on-grid” functionality) HYPE (hydrological model)	Design rains based on DDF-statistics; daily precipitation and temperature (from national gridded data)	Adjusted design rains; climate projections (daily time step; ~10 km or basin scale spatial resolution) from national portal

Requirements

Requirements can be divided into two sub-sections; one describing the types of input data required by the hydrological models, and one outlining the corresponding data requirements set out in recommendations and guidelines for NbS measures.

Modelling and input

The primary objective of *hydrological modelling* is to represent the movement of water and associated substances, through the landscape, from the moment it reaches the ground (as rainfall or melting snow), to rivers (via overland and subsurface pathways), and ultimately to the sea. The main output variable is streamflow (Figure 1a), while key inputs include precipitation and temperature, which are used to estimate snowmelt and evapotranspiration losses. Solar radiation is often included to estimate evapotranspiration.

Hydrological models typically operate at a daily time step, as applied in all NBSPLUS case studies. Model domains may range from individual catchments to continental or global scales, with spatial discretization commonly based on grid cells or hydrological response units (HRU).

In the context of NbS, spatial scale is a critical factor in selecting an appropriate modelling approach (Ruangpan et al., 2020). Large-scale interventions, such as wetlands, floodplains and detention located within or near the basin, if available. For larger-scale applications, it is preferable to use gridded input datasets, where station observations have been

structures (e.g. leaky dams; stormwater basins; reservoirs) are generally assessed using hydrological models that capture long-term catchment (e.g., water balance and flow) dynamics (Lalonde et al., 2024).

In contrast, small-scale urban NbS (e.g., rain gardens, green roofs, detention ponds) require high-resolution *hydrodynamic (hydraulic) models* to simulate short-term, localized processes such as runoff routing, flood extent, water depth and local drainage interactions (Pérez-Corredor et al., 2024). These models may take streamflow as input to simulate water overtopping riverbanks during fluvial flooding, and/or rainfall to represent pluvial or compound flooding. The models are computationally intensive and are therefore typically applied to smaller spatial domains, e.g., part of a city or river section. Note that the application of a more limited domain can lead to an incomplete understanding of e.g., flood event dynamics, especially in smaller catchments, when features or upstream contributions are missing (see e.g., Hill et al., 2023).

Long-term simulation

Hydrological modelling is generally performed as a long-term continuous simulation, to account for “hydrological memory”, i.e. the time it takes for water to travel through the landscape.

For single-basin applications, hydroclimatological inputs can often be obtained from meteorological stations interpolated and, in some cases, combined with additional data sources, e.g. weather radar-derived precipitation.

Event-based simulation

Hydrodynamic modelling is typically conducted as an event-based simulation to represent the temporal evolution and spatial extent of flooding. For *fluvial flooding*, i.e. riverbank overtopping, discharge is the primary input; while *pluvial flooding* (i.e. the local accumulation of excess short-duration extreme precipitation) is driven by rainfall. Compound flooding, resulting from the interaction of both processes, can also be simulated. The main output variable is maximum water depth (Figure 1b).

Event-based analyses are often based on synthetic “what-if” scenarios (stress testing; e.g. Albano et al., 2021), using extreme values associated with specified return periods (e.g. 10-, 50-, or 100-year events, representing levels exceeded on average once within those periods). These values are derived through *extreme-value analysis* of long-term observational records.

Short-duration rainfall extremes are commonly described using Intensity-Duration-Frequency (IDF) statistics (Figure 2a), which provide rainfall estimates for different rainfall durations and return periods.

Recommendations and guidelines

A comprehensive international review of guidelines for the hydroclimatological inputs in NbS design was beyond the scope of NBSPLUS. Instead, this section summarizes practices in the case study countries based on expert knowledge within the project.

In Spain, the Ministry for the Ecological Transition and the Demographic Challenge (MITECO) has adapted the International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN) framework, *Guidance for Using the IUCN Global Standard for Nature-based Solutions* (IUCN, 2020) to the Spanish context. This adaptation applies the eight

Figure 1. Examples of key model outputs: (a) time series of simulated (and observed) streamflow, estimated from a hydrological model (red line) compared to observations (green line), and (b) maximum water depth during a flood from a hydrodynamic model.

Figure 2. (a) Example of Depth-Duration Frequency (DDF) curves. Point values are based on extreme-value analysis of observations, to which lines have been fitted. (b) Schematic illustration of how climate factors are estimated, based on DDF curves from climate model projections representing different time periods.

criteria and 28 indicators defined in the IUCN standard to support the design and verification of NbS (MITECO, 2025). In addition, MITECO has developed an Informative Folder on NbS, which includes a “Decalogue of Key Initiatives” aimed at promoting the implementation of NbS in Spanish cities and strengthening their

alignment with the 2030 Agenda and the Spanish Urban Agenda. At the local scale, these national frameworks are reflected in initiatives such as the *Agenda Verde de Valencia 2030*, which promotes the integration of NbS within the city’s broader sustainable development strategy (CCV, 2022).

In Quebec, the design of urban water infrastructure is based on a range of event-based time series, typically covering return periods from 2- and 5-year events up to the 100-year event for high-impact flood protection. To account for climate change, observation-based return levels (e.g. 10-year rainfall) are commonly adjusted using a scaling factor, often referred to as a Climate Factor (CF) (e.g. Willems et al., 2012). The CF is generally derived from extreme-value analysis of short-duration rainfall in climate model projections (Figure 2b), and may vary depending on e.g. the selected future time horizon as well as the emission scenario. In practice, a baseline CF of ~1.2 is commonly applied in Quebec, corresponding to an assumed 20% increase in rainfall intensity.

In Sweden, guidance consists of both national-level recommendations and locally adapted practices. As a general example, stormwater ponds (or parks) are designed either for flood risk reduction or for water quality improvement, with corresponding design discharges linked to rainfall events of different return periods and durations. For local flood protection measures, recommended rainfall return periods typically range from 2 to 30 years, depending on factors such as land use and population density (Svenskt Vatten, 2016). For broader pluvial flood mapping and protection, a 100-year return period is commonly applied, adjusted using a CF in the range of 1.2-1.4 (MSB, 2023).

In Malmö, the Swedish case study city, pluvial flood protection measures in new development areas are typically designed to manage a 6-hour rainfall event with a 100-year return period and a CF of 1.3. For

blue-green (BG) solutions, no fixed design return period is applied – instead, it depends on factors such as the type and size of the area, as well as the primary function of the measure (e.g. local pluvial flood mitigation versus reduction of the sewer system load). For example, individual BG measures may be designed for a 5-year rainfall event, while the overall stormwater system is expected to accommodate a 20-year event.

Availability

This section is divided into two sub-sections: one covering historical observations, and one addressing future climate projections. It includes examples of the data available in the case studies as well as an overview of globally available datasets.

Historical observations

In Sweden, local data for the case study area come primarily from the national meteorological network operated by SMHI (Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute), complemented, where available, by observations from local water utilities (SMHI, 2026). At the national scale, several gridded hydroclimatological data products are available, generated either through meteorological reanalysis using Numerical Weather Prediction (NWP) models or through interpolation of station observations. Recently, a national high-resolution rainfall product, combining satellite, radar and station data (including Personal Weather Stations), has become operational. In addition, SMHI provides national DDF statistics at a regional scale.

In Spain, local daily observations of precipitation, temperature and radiation are available for the case study area. At the national level, AEMET (Agencia Estatal de Meteorología) provides extensive gridded datasets and interpolated station observations of precipitation, temperature and other climate variables at daily to monthly resolutions (AEMET, 2026).

In Canada, high-quality local monitoring data will be used to ensure that the models are well-calibrated to the

conditions of the specific case study. Nationally, station data from ECCC (Environment and Climate Change Canada) provide the most accurate historical data for different locations, including the raw data used to create the official DDF statistics (ECCC, 2026).

An overview of major globally available high-resolution observation-based forcing data, with a focus on precipitation, is provided in Table 2.

Table 2. Major sources of global high-resolution (<1 day; <0.5°) observation-based forcing data for hydrological prediction.

Dataset	Resolutions Start year	Description	URL for access
ERA5	0.25° / 1-hr 1940	Reanalysis with multiple variables	https://doi.org/10.24381/cds.adbb2d47
MSWEP	0.1° / 1-hr 1979	P from merging stations, satellite and reanalysis	https://www.gloh2o.org/
MSWX	0.1° / 3-hr 1979	Multiple variables from adjusted reanalysis	https://www.gloh2o.org/mswx/
IMERG	0.1° / 30-min 1998	P from multiple satellites	https://gpm.nasa.gov/data/directory
CMORPH	8-km / 30-min 1998	P from merging stations and satellite	https://doi.org/10.25921/w9va-q159

Future climate projections

Climate modelling is a rapidly evolving field. New models, and model generations, are developed and new simulations of future climate conditions are regularly produced and released. This dynamic situation poses major challenges for societal (urban and rural) planning (design and assessment), including for NbS.

For the NBSPLUS case studies, different sources of climate model data are available. In Spain, both AEMET and the

AdapteCCa.se portal provide regionally downscaled climate change projections. In Canada, the primary resource is the climate model ensemble developed by Ouranos, a regional climatology consortium based in Québec. Their CRCM5-CMIP6 model (~12 km resolution) is the standard for climate impact studies in the region. In Sweden, SMHI maintains an extensive catalogue of future climate projections, including from the EURO-CORDEX consortium (~12 km), which are also applicable in Spain. In addition, recent

very high-resolution (~3 km) projections are available, which are especially relevant for analyzing short-duration rainfall extremes and pluvial flooding.

As “raw” climate model data are challenging for non-experts to use, a range of climate services providing processed and user-friendly information have been developed (Weichselgartner and Arheimer, 2019). These services typically provide estimates of the expected future change in various *hydroclimatological indicators* for different locations, time horizons, and emission scenarios. Some indicators with particular relevance in an NbS context are presented in Table 3.

Examples of climate services from the NBSPLUS case studies include the Spanish CEAMMEV.es portal, which provides high-

resolution climatological information for the Valencian community. In Sweden, SMHI operates a national climate scenario service that delivers projections at the hydrological basin scale. In Canada, climate projection data are made available through different federally supported platforms including ClimateData.ca, CCDS (Canadian Climate Data and Scenarios) and PCIC (Pacific Climate Impacts Consortium).

Concerning global climate projection data, the primary resource is the Climate Data Store at the Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S; climate.copernicus.eu), implemented by ECMWF (European Centre for Medium-range Weather Forecasting).

Table 3. Commonly used climate indicators for different NbS-related hazards.

Hazard	Indicators
Extreme rainfall and pluvial flooding	For short-duration extremes, future change is commonly quantified by the climate factor CF (section 1.2). For daily or multi-day extremes, common indicators include RX1day (annual maximum 1-day precipitation) and RX5day (annual maximum 5-day precipitation).
Heatwaves	Changes in heatwave properties can be quantified by e.g. WSDI (warm-spell duration index, reflecting the annual count of days contributing to warm spells) and CSU (maximum number of consecutive days with daily maximum temperature > 25°C). A comprehensive indicator to estimate outdoor human thermal stress is the Universal Thermal Comfort Index (UTCI), which combines air temperature and relative humidity with wind and radiation.
Drought	Drought indicators generally quantify statistical anomalies relative to long-term local conditions and capture different components of the hydrological cycle (e.g. precipitation, soil moisture, river discharge, groundwater) or their impacts, such as vegetation stress (WMO, 2016). Common indicators include CDD (maximum number of consecutive dry days, with daily precipitation < 1 mm), which reflects dry spell length, a key factor in drought onset. The SPI (standardized precipitation index) and SPEI (standardized precipitation evapotranspiration index) both quantify deviations from “normal” conditions over recent months and are widely used to characterize meteorological drought (WMO, 2016). Hydrological drought is often monitored using the LFI (low-flow index), based on exceedance-threshold approaches to quantify deficits in river discharge or reservoir storage. In Europe, the CDI (combined drought indicator) provides a composite measure to track agricultural drought onset, its spatiotemporal evolution, and recovery.

Concluding remarks

Hydroclimatological modelling for NbS design and evaluation requires different types of input data, depending on spatial scale, NbS (multi-)functionality, modelling approach (e.g. continuous or event-based), and the treatment of future climate conditions.

The case study overview illustrates how recommendations and guidelines on the input varies between and within countries, reflecting local practices and design principles. It is important that generalized NbS services are able to accommodate this diversity while still meeting the needs of each individual user.

Across the NBSPLUS case studies, data availability is broadly comparable. Historical observations are accessible through local monitoring networks and national datasets, while future projections are provided via established climate services.

Several key global resources are also available to support NbS-focused hydroclimatological stress testing in regions where local observational data are limited or absent. Within NBSPLUS, these data will be applied across the three use cases to demonstrate stress testing at multiple scales and to assess the potential for transferability to other locations.

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